

Study of Some Transition Metal Complexes of Amethopterin

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The avidity of amethopterin, 4-amino-*N*¹⁰-methylpteroylglutamic acid (AMPGA) for the ions of heavy metals, Mn²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Cu²⁺, have been measured and recorded in the form of stability constants and free energy changes, using Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti at 35° and at various ionic strengths, viz. 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M with KNO₃. The order of stability obtained for the metal ions indicates that the Mellor-Maley sequence is not strictly adhered to, the principal change being a strong depression of the constant for Cu²⁺ ion. Probable structure to the isolated chelates have been assigned on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data.

TRANSITION metals present in traces in the body change the behaviour of enzyme system by binding with them and alter the structures and functions of genetic materials by acting with nucleic acids which may be manifested in the formation of cancer. Structural analogue of normal pteroyl compounds, folic acid antagonist have been shown quite important in experimental cancer therapy, mainly in Leukemia¹. The highest antileukemic activity is found in the compounds with a 4-amino group. Amethopterin (1) has in addition to 4-amino group, a methyl group in the 10-position.

1

Chelation study of folic acid with several metal ions like Cu²⁺, Ni²⁺, Zn²⁺, Co²⁺, Cd²⁺, Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺, Mg²⁺, has been done by Albert⁷. The comparison

of K_{st} , free energy change (ΔG°) and thereby the free metal in equilibrium with the chelate may give good information for an understanding of the chelate hypothesis in cancer problem. Also, since some metal salts and metal chelates are used as anti-cancer compounds, the metal chelate formed under physiological pH conditions may be used for the inhibition of tumour. This communication reports the thermodynamic stability constants and the free energy changes (ΔG°) for the interaction of amethopterin with the transition metal ions, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺ and Mn²⁺, using Bjerrum-Calvin pH titration technique² as adopted by Irving and Rossotti³ at 35° and 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M ionic strengths with KNO₃. Probable structures of the isolated chelates have been assigned on the basis of elemental analyses and spectral data.

Experimental

Conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations, employing the monovariation method⁴, were done to study the preliminary stoichiometry.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TRANSITIONAL METAL COMPLEXES OF AMPGA AT 35° AND VARIOUS IONIC CONCENTRATIONS*

Ionic strength <i>M</i>	log K_{st}	Mn ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Cu ²⁺ **
0.05	log K_1	7.15 (7.20)	7.25 (7.25)	7.00 (7.10)	6.45 (6.55)
	log K_2	6.20 (6.10)	6.60 (6.70)	5.80 (5.75)	5.85 (5.65)
	log β_2	13.35 (13.30)	13.85 (13.95)	12.80 (12.85)	12.30 (12.20)
0.1	log K_1	8.00 (7.85)	7.90 (7.80)	7.85 (7.75)	6.85 (7.00)
	log K_2	7.10 (6.80)	7.20 (7.25)	6.25 (6.35)	5.95 (5.95)
	log β_2	15.10 (14.65)	15.10 (15.05)	14.10 (14.10)	12.80 (12.95)
0.2	log K_1	8.80 (8.90)	8.95 (8.95)	8.90 (8.85)	7.60 (7.75)
	log K_2	7.65 (7.80)	7.60 (7.85)	6.85 (6.75)	6.55 (6.60)
	log β_2	16.45 (16.70)	16.55 (16.80)	15.75 (15.60)	14.15 (14.35)

* Values in paranthesis obtained by the best least-square fits.

** Ref. 5.

Solution of amethopterin was prepared by percolating an aqueous solution of the sodium salt (Lederte, U.S.A) through the cation exchanger resin (H-form), Amberlite IR-120 and standardising the regenerated acid against a standard alkali (KOH).

For potentiometric titrations, the following mixtures (total volume 50 ml) were titrated against 0.1 M KOH.

- (A) 5 ml of 0.02 M HNO₃,
- (B) A + 20 ml of 0.004 M AMPGA solution,
- (C) B + 5 ml of 0.002 M metal ion solution.

The ionic strength of the solution was maintained at 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 M by KNO₃ solution, keeping the total volume 50 ml. Pure nitrogen was bubbled through the titration cell. Further, with the use of very dilute solutions (2 × 10⁻⁴ M) of the metal ions, possibility of the formation of polynuclear complexes was minimised. The values of thermodynamic stability constants are recorded in Tables 1 and 2. The values of log K₁ and log K₂ were recorded

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC CONSTANTS AND FREE ENERGY CHANGES OF AMPGA COMPLEXES AT 35°

	Mn ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II} *
log K ₁ , μ=0	5.65	5.80	5.55	5.35
log K ₂ , μ=0	4.75	5.10	4.20	4.95
log β ₂ , μ=0	10.40	10.90	9.75	10.25
ΔG ₁ ⁰ , kcal mol ⁻¹	8.02	8.23	7.87	7.57
ΔG ₂ ⁰	6.74	7.24	5.96	7.02
ΔG ⁰	14.76	15.47	13.83	14.59

* Ref. 5.

directly from the formation curves and refined by the method of least squares.

For the study of the attachment site of ligand (AMPGA) with metal ions Cu^{II} and Co^{II} chelates were isolated by refluxing aqueous solutions of the

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL DATA AND IR FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF AMPGA COMPLEXES

	Ligand		
	C ₃₀ H ₂₂ O ₈ N ₂	Na ₂ CuL ₂ ·2H ₂ O*	Na ₂ CoL ₂ ·2H ₂ O*
Analysis % :			
Found/	C - 46.14 (45.73)	46.3 (45.93)	4.23 (4.21)
(Calcd.)	H - 4.16 (4.19)	21.75 (21.43)	5.60 (5.64)
	N - 21.50 (21.34)		
	M - 6.00 (6.05)		
NH strength	3500, 3400 3300 b.b.	3100-3500 b.b. 3400, 3000, 3200	3100-3500 b.b.
Tert. N	980, 1020	980, 1020	980, 1020
Sec. amide			
ν (CONH)	1635 1660	1635, 1660	1635, 1660
ν _{as} COO ⁻			
(V ₁)	1590, 1560	1690, 2680	1690, 1680
ν _{as} COO ⁻			
(V ₂)	1375	1365	1390
	1360	1320	1350
Δν (V ₁ - V ₂)	215	325	300
Coordinated		3100, 3550	3100, 3500
H ₂ O	-	1610, 830	1610, 830

* L-C₃₀H₂₂O₈N₂

metal salt and the ligand in 1 : 2 molar ratio for 2 to 3 h. The insoluble complex separated out on cooling was washed, dried in vacuum and stored in air-tight bottles. The composition of the chelates was ascertained by estimating metal, carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen (Table 3).

Results and Discussion

The conductometric and potentiometric (pH) titrations indicate the formation of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes. The value of n̄ in all the cases was found to be <2, confirming the formation of ML and ML₂ type complexes (L=AMPGA).

Scheme 1

The nature of the pH titration curves for mixtures (B) and (C) (Fig. 1) shows that the first step acid dissociation of AMPGA is influenced by these metal ions, contrary to the mechanism observed in case of Cu^{II} where the first step acid dissociation of 1 is not affected by Cu^{II} (Scheme 1). Thus, two equivalent of acid are liberated per mole of the ligand both in the absence and presence of the metal ions, showing that the stepwise complex formation with AMPGA takes place through deprotonation of both the COOH groups simultaneously, as shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

An analysis of the formation curves (Fig. 2) indicates that these metals follow different patterns

Fig. 1. pH-Titration curves, AMPGA-systems : (A) acid, (B) ligand, (C) complex curves and — with Cu^{2+} , -- with other metal ions.

the titration. As a result, this 1 : 1 complex must be able to compete strongly with the free metal cations for the unbound complex forming species (amethopterin).

A perusal of Tables 1 and 2, and Fig. 3 show that the constants, in almost every case, are higher than those of pteroylglutamic acid. This heightened avidity is most likely, due to presence of the 4-amino group (in place of OH group) in amethopterin, thus making it more basic than pteroylglutamic acid. Further, the results obtained in this investigation do not confirm to the Mellor-Maley⁶ sequence: $\text{Cu}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} > \text{Fe}^{2+} > \text{Mn}^{2+}$. The principal change being a strong depression of the constant for Cu^{2+} and a strong increase of the same for Co^{2+} and Mn^{2+} . Similar depression of the constant for Cu^{2+} and a high avidity for Co^{2+} has been reported in the case of pteroylglutamic acid⁷. The cause of this depression may well be a certain amount of steric hindrance as predicted by Albert⁷, because Cu^{2+} alone forms planar complexes.

The analytical data (Table 3) in confirmation with the conductometric studies indicate 1 : 2 (M : L)

Fig. 2. Formation curves of chelates : [A] Mn^{2+} , [B] Co^{2+} , [C] Ni^{2+} , [D] Cu^{2+} ; —○— 0.05, —●— 0.1, —⊙— 0.2 M.

of addition to amethopterin molecules. The complexation with Mn^{2+} and Ni^{2+} follows the sequence of independent addition. First, one atom of the metal combined with one molecule of amethopterin. The 1 : 1 complex thus formed did not appreciably combine with a second molecule of amethopterin to give the 1 : 2 complex, until at least more than 80% of the 1 : 1 complex had been formed. The addition of Co^{2+} and Cu^{2+} to amethopterin molecules, on the other hand, is shown to be dependent. Thus, no appreciable quantity of the 1 : 1 complex accumulated even in the first half of

stoichiometry of the isolated complexes, with the molecular formula $\text{ML}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The isolated complexes were found insoluble in water and were infusible below 350° .

The ir data (Table 3) clearly shows that while most of the bands of the ligand remain unchanged in complexation, there is a considerable shift in the frequencies of the carbonyl group indicating that chelation with the metal ions takes place through the carboxylic groups (Structure 2). The frequency

with metal ions in pteroylglutamic acid (folic acid) has been shown to be N_5 and 4-hydroxy group (cf. 8-hydroxy quinoline)⁷. But this takes place relatively at higher pH (>7), where the ionisation of 4-hydroxyl group becomes substantial. In lower pH range, however, pteroylglutamic acid has also been shown to involve its carboxylic groups for attachment with metal ions⁷. The absence of hydroxyl group at 4-position in AMPGA and the pH range of its interaction with the metal ions (pH 2.5-6.0) support the proposed site of attachment. This finds further confirmation in the ir data of the isolated chelates.

Fig. 3. Extrapolation of log K to zero ionic-concentration.

separation ($\Delta\nu$) along with the shift of the band from 1580 to $\sim 1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicates the presence of considerable covalence in metal to ligand bond in these complexes.

The bands near 3200, 1600 and 840 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of coordinated water in these complexes.

Attachment of metal ion at the carboxylic groups (cf. salt formation) may seem to be unusual in the light of the fact that the normal site of chelation

Thus, in the light of the above observations, the general structure of the metal chelates may be as in Structure 2. The formation of only two chelates (ML and ML_2) with AMPGA molecule acting as a bidentate ligand shows that only four coordination positions of the metal ions are saturated with this ligand. Thus, two coordination positions remain unsaturated with the hexavalent metal ions. This may favour the attachment of the chelates with the tissue. Thus, amethopterin chelates of these metals may have beneficial effects in the treatment of cancer.

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